

NOTES

Preparation and Characterisation of Naphthoxides of Aluminium(III)

K. C. MALHOTRA, (Miss) VIMALAMMA T. ABRAHAM
and
(Mrs.) NEERAJ SHARMA*

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University,
Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005

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THE chemistry of metal naphthoxides like those of metal alkoxides^{1,2} and phenoxides^{3,4} involves the study of M—O—C moiety. But unlike alkoxides and phenoxides, very little information is available on metal naphthoxides despite their wide industrial applications^{5,6}. Nevertheless a few scattered references are available on the preparation of metal naphthoxides^{7,8}. Dimeric naphthoxides of niobium(v) and tantalum(v) have been characterised only recently⁹. Acceptor properties of naphthoxides of titanium(IV) has also been established¹⁰. It is therefore of great interest to prepare and characterise naphthoxides of aluminium(III) and to establish their acceptor properties which may be helpful to explore their use as polymerisation catalysts.

Experimental

Anhydrous AlCl₃ (B.D.H.) was purified by sublimation in an atmosphere of chlorine, and the

excess of chlorine removed under vacuum. Purity of the compound was checked by elemental analysis. 2-Naphthol (B.D.H.) was crystallised twice from hot carbon tetrachloride. The sample with m.p. 121–22° was used for various reactions. *p*-Xylene and the three ligands used were of A.R. grade and were further purified by the methods described elsewhere¹¹.

Naphthoxides of composition AlCl₂(ONp) and AlCl(ONp)₂ (where, ONp stands for C₁₀H₇O⁻ ion) were prepared by refluxing aluminium(III) chloride and 2-naphthol in predetermined 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios in excess of dry xylene till there was no evolution of HCl gas. The resulting compounds were filtered, washed repeatedly with dry xylene and finally dried under vacuum. In case of Al(ONp)₃, however, the reactants went into xylene and the compound was isolated by the addition of petroleum ether to the resulting solution and dried in vacuum. Elemental analyses (Table 1) were in good agreement with the proposed formula for the compounds. Addition compounds of naphthoxy derivatives of aluminium(III) of composition AlCl₂(ONp) and AlCl(ONp)₂ with pyridine, α -picoline and pyridine-*N*-oxide were obtained by reacting suspension of parent naphthoxide in benzene with the base. The reactants were stirred for 8 h and allowed to stand overnight when a solid crystalline compound separated out.

Aluminium in the complexes was estimated gravimetrically by oxine method as Al(C₉H₆ON)₃, while chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF NAPHTHOXIDES OF Al^{III} AND ADDUCTS

Ligand	Complex	Colour of complex	Decom. temp. °C	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)		Mol. wt : Found/(Calcd)	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
				Al	Cl		
2-Naphthol	AlCl ₂ (ONp)	Dirty white	235	11.18 (11.20)	29.42 (29.46)	478 (241)	2.3
2-Naphthol	AlCl(ONp) ₂	Light brown	229	7.78 (7.75)	10.24 (10.19)	700 (348.5)	1.8
2-Naphthol	Al(ONp) ₃	Dirty white	193 ^a	5.89 (5.92)	—	1802 (456)	1.3
Pyridine	AlCl ₂ (ONp).py	White	184	8.48 (8.44)	22.14 (22.19)	—	2.4
α -Picoline	AlCl ₂ (ONp). α -pic	White	180	8.11 (8.09)	21.91 (21.26)	341 (334)	1.0
Pyridine- <i>N</i> -oxide	AlCl ₂ (ONp).pyO	White	172	8.10 (8.03)	21.15 (21.13)	340 (336)	2.7
Pyridine	AlCl(ONp) ₂ .py	White	158	6.29 (6.32)	8.32 (8.30)	450 (427.5)	3.2
α -Picoline	AlCl ₂ (ONp) ₂ . α -pic	White	197	6.19 (6.11)	8.09 (8.04)	435 (442)	1.5
Pyridine- <i>N</i> -oxide	AlCl(ONp) ₂ .pyO	White	95	6.12 (6.08)	8.04 (8.00)	450 (443.5)	3.5

^aM.p.

The conductance measurements of all the complexes in nitrobenzene were made on a Elico conductivity bridge using a cell of cell constant 0.334 cm^{-1} at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Molar conductance of the complexes were calculated (Table 1). The molecular weight determinations by cryoscopic method of the complexes were carried out in nitrobenzene. The ir spectra (nujol) of the complexes were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer double grating infrared spectrophotometer in the region $4000 - 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

The compounds were moisture-sensitive and changed colour on exposure to moist air but were sufficiently stable in dry air. Like the rare earth phenoxides^{13,15}, the solubility of the naphthoxides in organic solvents, viz. benzene, chlorobenzene, nitrobenzene *etc.* increased as the number of naphthoxy groups bonded to aluminium increased. Molar conductance (Δ_M) values of $10^{-3} M$ solutions in nitrobenzene suggested non-ionic nature of these compounds. Molecular weight determinations by cryoscopic methods in nitrobenzene indicated dimeric nature of $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{ONp})$, $\text{AlCl}(\text{ONp})_2$ at low concentrations. The extent of association increased as the concentration of the solute increased. $\text{Al}(\text{ONp})_3$ was found to be a trimer at all concentration in nitrobenzene. This behaviour was quite similar to the one observed for aluminium alkoxide and phenoxide¹⁴. The broad ir band for 2-naphthol in the region $3360 - 3460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to hydrogen bonded naphtholic hydroxyl group¹⁶ was absent in all the naphthoxides. The lowering of $\nu_{\text{O-C}}$ (1260 cm^{-1}) of 2-naphthol by about $30 - 40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on naphthoxide formation was due to the attachment of the naphthoxy oxygen to aluminium. This was supported by the appearance of new bands (not shown by the pure ligand) in the lower wave number region. The ir band in the region $575 - 595 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was assigned to $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ vibration¹⁷. For $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{ONp})$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{ONp})_2$ the bands observed at 528 and 533 cm^{-1} , respectively, were assigned to

the bridging $\text{Al} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{array} \text{Al}$ modes^{18,19} since these bands are expected to lie at the lower wave number regions as compared to the terminal ones. The $480 - 490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ band was assigned to the terminal aluminium-chlorine stretching modes in tetrahedral stereochemistry²⁰. No band due to bridging chlorine was observed.

Thus based on these experimental evidences the following dimeric structures (I) and (II) for $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{ONp})$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{ONp})_2$ may be suggested, respectively. Two types of aluminium-oxygen stretching modes have been observed in the spectrum of $\text{Al}(\text{ONp})_3$, viz. 580 and 540 cm^{-1} , suggesting two types of aluminium-oxygen bonds in this compound. The sharp 580 cm^{-1} band was assigned to the terminal aluminium-oxygen stretching modes while the 540 cm^{-1} band was assigned to the bridging aluminium-oxygen-aluminium bond.

No band due to Al-Cl band was observed for this compound. Thus the presence of two types of aluminium-oxygen bonds could only be explained by the structure (III).

Unlike alkoxides of aluminium, phenomenon of aging has not been observed in the case of aluminium naphthoxides when left over for some time.

The naphthoxides, $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{ONp})$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{ONp})_2$ formed addition compounds $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{ONp})_2 \cdot \text{L}$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{ONp})_3 \cdot \text{L}$ with heterocyclic N-bases, viz. L = pyridine (py), α -picoline (α -pic) and pyridine-N-oxide (pyNO). The molar conductance values in nitrobenzene correspond to their non-ionic nature. Molecular weight data in nitrobenzene correspond to monomeric species. Formation of the adducts involves ring opening of the dimeric naphthoxides at the central aluminium which still retains its coordination number of four. A breakdown of structure of parent naphthoxide has been ascertained from the shifting of the ir band due to

$\text{Al} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{array} \text{Al}$ to higher wave number regions characteristic of $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ on adduct formation. Therefore, the sharp band in the region $575 - 595 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these addition compounds was assigned to the terminal $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$. The formation of a bond between the nitrogen of pyridine and α -picoline and the metal in the addition compounds, increases the electron density on the latter. Consequently, the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ at 1578 cm^{-1} in pyridine²¹ and 1583 cm^{-1} in α -picoline^{22,23} shifted towards higher wave number side in the addition compounds. A strong and sharp band in the region $460 - 520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Al-N)²⁴ in the complexes further confirms the formation of

coordinate bond from nitrogen to aluminium. Coordination of oxygen of pyridine-*N*-oxide to aluminium as observed by a shift of 1240 (ν_{N-O})²⁵ and 840 cm^{-1} (δ_{N-O})²⁶ to lower wave number region. Probably due to the stability of the six-membered ring structure of $\text{Al}(\text{ONp})_3$, it did not give addition compounds with these ligands.

Thus the parent naphthoxides except $\text{Al}(\text{ONp})_3$, on adduct formation with bases, suffer a breakdown of polymeric structure and readily form monomeric addition compounds suggesting the stability of aluminium-nitrogen bond in preference to aluminium-oxygen bond and also relaxation of strain is experienced in polymeric structures (I) and (II).

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium with Glycine and Malonic Acid.

A Polarographic Study

KRISHNA NEMA and FARID KHAN*

Department of Chemistry,
Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 008

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A few binary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine and malonic acid have been reported in the literature¹⁻³. Some mixed ligand complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine and other complexing agents have also been studied⁴. The survey of literature reveals no report on the study of mixed ligand complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine and malonic acid and hence thought worthwhile to undertake the present investigation.

Experimental

AnalR grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions. Double-distilled water was used to prepare the solutions of cadmium chloride, glycine and malonic acid. The overall concentrations of Cd^{II} , KCl and gelatin in the test solutions were 1.0 mM, 1.00 M and 0.01%, respectively.

Current-voltage curves were obtained by means of a Toshniwal PL-50 manual polarograph using polyflex galvanometer. The capillary characteristics ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$) in KCl ($\mu = 1.00 M$) at $E_{d.e.} = -0.61 V$ vs S.C.E. and $h = 60 \text{ cm}$ at $42 \pm 0.1^\circ$ were $2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for deoxygenation. A Elico LI-10 needle type pH meter was used to measure pH of the test solution to 9.20 ± 0.10 , adjusted with dilute solution of NaOH and HCl (A.R.).

The depolariser and ligands (glycine and malonic acid) were taken in the concentration ratio 1 : 50 and current-voltage curves were drawn at different pH. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ is maximum at pH 9.20 ± 0.10 and hence the same pH was chosen for the present study. Identical conditions were maintained in simple and mixed complexes for determining the values of stability constants.

A number of current-voltage curves were obtained for binary complexes prior to the study of ternary complexes.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} gives a well defined two-electron reversible reduction wave in 1.0 M KCl⁵. The single wave was observed in each set of test solution. All the plots of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ gave straight lines with slope $30 \pm \text{mV}$ (mean value) showing two-electron reversible reduction wave of Cd^{II} and its complexes.

Cd-glycinate system: Glycine behaves as an acid and a base in water⁶. Its pK values ($\text{p}K_1 = 2.40$